

Solvent tolerance in Gram-negative bacteria

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SUMMARY

Bacteria have been found in all niches explored on Earth, their ubiquity derives from their enormous metabolic diversity and their capacity to adapt to changes in the environment. Some bacterial strains are able to thrive in the presence of high concentrations of toxic organic chemicals, such as aromatic compounds, aliphatic alcohols and solvents. The extrusion of these toxic compounds from the cell to the external medium represents the most relevant aspect in the solvent tolerance of bacteria, however, solvent tolerance is a multifactorial process that involves a wide range of genetic and physiological changes to overcome solvent damage. These additional elements include reduced membrane permeabilization, implementation of a stress response programme, and in some cases degradation of the toxic compound. We discuss the recent advances in our understanding of the mechanisms involved in solvent tolerance and how solvent-tolerant strains may offer new biotechnological avenues.

Introduction

Organic solvents encompass a vast number of compounds with different chemical structures, such as benzene rings and aliphatic alcohols; many of these compounds are harmful to microorganisms, plants, animals and humans. Organic solvents accumulate in cell membranes and disorganise their structure, which results in a loss of ions, metabolites, changes the intracellular pH and membrane electrical potential, and eventually leads to cell death (Sikkema *et al.*, 1995; Ramos *et al.*, 2011). Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes (BTEX), are among the top 50 products fabricated on a Global-scale. The OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) has warned its member states of the relevance of aromatic hydrocarbon pollution and it has urged member states to pay attention to this problem and requested measures to deal with these pollutants and their abatement (OECD, 1995). The increasing demand for non-renewable fuels has forced the utilization and synthesis of biofuels, with ethanol and more recently *n*-butanol being the most promising options to replace the oil-derivatives in the market. Solvent tolerant bacteria with biodegradative properties are envisaged as the best alternative in bioremediation of heavily polluted sites; and because of their ability to thrive in the presence of high concentrations of toxic chemicals they are being considered model systems for the biosynthesis of chemicals such as ethanol, *n*-butanol and catechol derivatives (Nielsen *et al.*, 2009; Neumann *et al.*, 2005). In this mini-review we explore the mechanisms bacteria use to overcome the toxicity of organic solvents.

Changes in the cell membrane

Organic solvents accumulate in bacterial membranes increasing membrane fluidity (Sikkema et al., 1995; Bernal *et al.*, 2007b) and many microorganisms respond to solvents at the membrane level by counteracting the increase in fluidity caused by the partition of the solvent into the lipid bilayer. In the short-term some bacteria (of the genus *Pseudomonas* and *Vibrio*) respond by implementing isomerisation of the *cis* unsaturated fatty acids to *trans* unsaturated fatty acids, a reaction mediated by the *cis-trans* isomerase (reviewed in Heipiepper *et al.*, 2003). The isomerisation results in bacteria with denser membranes and a selective advantage allowing cells to adapt immediately to the new environmental conditions.

Bacteria can also change the saturated-to-unsaturated fatty acid ratio (Baer *et al.*, 1987; Pinkart and White, 1997; Alsaker *et al.*, 2010) and in other cases the length of the acyl-chains (Pinkart and White 1997). Increased levels of PlsX (fatty acid/phospholipid biosynthesis) and FabF [3-oxoacyl-(acyl-carrier-protein) synthase II] were found in the solvent tolerant mutant Rh8 of *Clostridium acetobutylicum* and their enhanced expression lead to an increase in membrane saturated fatty acid content and to enhanced solvent tolerance (Alkaser *et al.*, 2010). These fatty acid changes allow a denser membrane packing and contribute to solvent tolerance; but since *de novo* biosynthesis is required, these are considered long-term adaptation processes.

Changes in phospholipid head groups have also been shown to be involved in solvent tolerance (Sikkema *et al.*, 1995; Ramos *et al.*, 1997; Rühl *et al.*, 2011).

However, it is not clear if the changes in relative phospholipid content corresponded with an increased packing order in the membrane. In a cardiolipin-deficient mutant of *P. putida* DOT-T1E it has been speculated that changes in the membrane architecture, as a consequence of low cardiolipin content, provokes a decrease in the efficiency of the efflux pumps which is translated into reduced solvent tolerance of this mutant strain when compared with respect to the wild-type (Bernal *et al.*, 2007a).

The cyclopropane fatty acids (CFAs) have long been recognized as an important determinant of acid and alcohol resistance in *Escherichia coli* (Chang and Cronan, 1999). Expression of the *cfa* synthase gene is dependent on the RpoS sigma factor and it takes place when cells enter the stationary phase (Chang and Cronan, 1999; Pini *et al.*, 2009; Pini *et al.*, 2011). Two lines of evidence assign a role to the CFAs in solvent tolerance; a *cfaB* mutant of *P. putida* DOT-T1E is more sensitive to toluene shock than the parental strain (Pini *et al.*, 2009) and a *C. acetobutylicum* strain that overexpressed the *cfa* synthase gene showed increased butanol tolerance (Zhao *et al.*, 2003). In contrast with other genes from the toluene tolerance regulon, *cfaB* expression is not enhanced in response to the presence of toluene in *P. putida* (Domínguez-Cuevas, *et al.*, 2006; Duque *et al.*, 2007, Pini *et al.*, 2009) although the expression is reduced 4-fold in the presence of *o*-xylene (Dominguez-Cuevas, *et al.*, 2006), however in *C. acetobutylicum* CFA synthase levels increased 10 minutes after the addition of butanol (Alsaker *et al.*, 2010).

Comparative membrane proteome analysis of the *C. acetobutylicum* Rh8 butanol tolerant mutant and the parental strain *C. acetobutylicum* DSM 1731 during acidogenic and solventogenic phases identified, among others, 19 proteins whose expression levels were higher in the solventogenic phase than in the acidogenic phase and also higher in the solvent tolerant mutant Rh8 than in the wild-type strain. Of these proteins, 37% were involved in membrane structure and surface stabilization suggesting that stabilization of the membrane structure and surface is a requirement of increased solvent tolerance (Mao *et al.*, 2011). Goodarzi and colleagues (2010) also pointed out the importance of a number of cell-wall structural components in solvent tolerance; *E. coli* mutants in *slt* (encoding a murein-degrading soluble lytic transglycosylase) or strains that overexpressed *murB* (the enzyme that catalyzes the production of UDP-GlcNAc-enoylpyruvate) showed higher survival rates at 7% ethanol than the wild-type.

Interestingly, two proteins involved in flagellar assembly and synthesis (FlgE and Hag) were down-regulated in the *C. acetobutylicum* Rh8 butanol-tolerant mutant (Mao *et al.*, 2011). This agrees with previous data that showed that flagellar biosynthesis was down-regulated in the solventogenesis phase in *C. acetobutylicum*, in *E. coli* cells exposed to ethanol and in *P. putida* KT2440 in the presence of toluene (Alsaker and Papoutsakis, 2005; Dominguez-Cuevas *et al.*, 2006 ; Horinouchi *et al.*, 2010). This contrasts with the situation in *P. putida* DOT-T1E in which the expression level of flagellar genes was kept at a high level and the cells exhibited positive chemotaxis towards this compound (Lacal

et al., 2011). Involvement of flagellar proteins in tolerance has been previously described in other solvent-tolerant *P. putida* strains (Kieboom *et al.*, 2001b; Segura *et al.* 2001, 2004); in support of this role is that knockout-mutants in specific flagellar genes in these strains showed diminished solvent tolerance.

Certain strains when exposed to toxic chemicals produced membrane vesicles composed of phospholipids, exopolysaccharides and proteins. This has been proposed to serve as an active mechanism to release solvents accumulated in the cell surfaces (Kobayashi *et al.*, 2000), or to modify the hydrophobicity of cell surfaces. In fact, *P. putida* DOT-T1E cells increased their hydrophobicity, shifted their outer membrane lipopolysaccharide composition toward more hydrophobic and lower molecular forms and released vesicles in response to long chain alkanols (Baumgarten *et al.*, 2011).

Chaperones involved in solvent tolerance

All the proteomic and transcriptomic assays completed so far to identify cellular responses toward organic solvents, even those performed to evaluate the effect of low concentrations of toxic chemicals, have shown that the presence of the organic solvent imposes a stress on the culture that the cell has to overcome (Segura *et al.*, 2005; Dominguez-Cuevas *et al.*, 2006; Volkers *et al.*, 2006, Alkaser *et al.* 2010, Horinouchi *et al.*, 2010; Goodarzi *et al.*, 2010; Roma-Rodrigues *et al.*, 2010; Wijte *et al.*, 2011). In most of these assays, proteins or genes from the category of “heat stress response” (*groES*, *groL*, *grpE*, *dnaK*) were overexpressed in the presence of solvents such as ethanol, butanol, toluene

or xylenes. In fact, it has been well established that the *rpoH* regulon is up-regulated in the presence of several alcohols (Brynildsen and Liao, 2009; Rutherford *et al.*, 2010). The presence of organic solvents in the cytoplasm and periplasm alter protein folding; thus it is not surprising that production of diverse chaperones is necessary to cope with the presence of the solvent.

Several studies have also demonstrated that alcohols and aromatic compounds activate the response against oxidative agents and even provoke typical oxidative damage. This unique observation is most likely because in the presence of solvents the electron transport systems do not function properly and this leads to an increase in the production of hydrogen peroxide and other reactive oxygen species (Dominguez-Cuevas *et al.*, 2006; Brynildsen and Liao; 2009; Horinouchi *et al.*, 2010). In response to oxidative stress several genes of the OxyR regulon are induced by toluene in *P. putida* KT2440 (Dominguez-Cuevas *et al.*, 2006), and genes regulated by OxyR or NrdR are commonly up-regulated in *E. coli* ethanol tolerant strains (Horinouchi *et al.*, 2010).

Efflux pumps that enhance solvent tolerance

Efflux pumps, especially those belonging to the RND family, are considered the most efficient mechanism of solvent tolerance in Gram negative bacteria (Ramos *et al.*, 2002). RND transporters are proton-driven efflux systems (Daniels *et al.*, 2009) constituted by three proteins which form a multicomponent complex extending from the inner membrane to the outer membrane (Figure 1, Eswaran *et al.*, 2004; Murakami *et al.*, 2008). This

molecular organisation permits bacteria to expulse compounds via two possible pathways: from the periplasm to the external medium or from the cytoplasm to the external medium (Nikaido and Takatsuka, 2009). Members of the ABC-transporters (ATP Binding Cassette) have also been implicated in solvent tolerance (Kim *et al.*, 1998; 2009; García *et al.*, 2010).

Most Gram negative bacteria encode several RND efflux pumps in their genomes (up to 20 in the highly solvent tolerant strain *P. putida* DOT-T1E [Godoy *et al.*, 2010]). Survival analysis of *P. putida* DOT-T1E cultures after toluene shock (addition of a second phase of toluene) revealed that three RND efflux pumps, with different but overlapping substrate specificity, are directly involved in toluene resistance (Figure 2; Ramos *et al.*, 2002). The presence of TtgGHI, encoded on the 133-kb pGRT1 plasmid, was found to be absolutely necessary to survive a 0.3% (v/v) toluene shock (Rodríguez-Herva *et al.*, 2007; Molina *et al.*, 2011). The pGRT1 has high stability and is self-transmissible to other *P. putida* strains, thus constituting a valuable tool for biotechnological processes.

Although from a quantitative point of view, TtgGHI plays a major role in solvent removal, the complex regulation of the three efflux pumps suggests that the coordinated expression of the two chromosomal (*ttgABC* and *ttgDEF*) and the plasmid encoded *ttgGHI* efflux pump operons confers the high level of resistance displayed by *P. putida* DOT-T1E (Ramos *et al.*, 2002).

In the last five years, extensive analysis of the regulation of the *ttgABC* and *ttgGHI* operons, has been carried out. TtgR which belongs to the TetR family of

regulators is the specific transcriptional repressor of the *ttgABC*. The basal expression of this pump is increased in the presence of antibiotics, flavonoids and alcohols but it does not vary in the presence of aromatic compounds (Duque *et al.*, 2001; Rojas *et al.*, 2004; Daniels *et al.*, 2010). The TtgR operator is a 36 pb sequence located in the *ttgR-ttgA* intergenic region and overlaps the -10 and -35 regions of the *ttgABC* promoter, and the -10 region of the *ttgR* promoter. In the absence of effectors, the TtgR dimer is bound to its operator site repressing its own expression and that of the efflux pump; effector binding to the protein-DNA complex induces the dissociation of TtgR, and allows transcription (Krell *et al.*, 2007). The crystal structure of the TtgR protein in complex with effectors has been determined (Alguet *et al.*, 2007). TtgR has a hydrophobic binding pocket an observation which explains TtgR's ability to bind different ligands. Within this pocket two binding sites were identified, one that binds ligands with high affinity and the second which binds molecules with low affinity.

TtgV belongs to the IclR family of transcriptional regulators and is the main regulator in the modulation of the expression of *ttgDEF* and *ttgGHI* (reviewed in Fillet *et al.*, 2011b). The *ttgDEF* is silent in the absence of effectors, while a basal expression level of the *ttgGHI* operon has been reported (Rojas *et al.*, 2004; Guazzaroni *et al.*, 2004; 2005). Exposure of *P. putida* DOT-T1E to aromatic compounds (i.e., 4-nitrotoluene, benzonitrile, 1-naphthol) and aliphatic alcohols, increased the transcription rate of *ttgDEF* and *ttgGHI* (Guazzaroni *et al.*, 2005). TtgV is a tetramer in solution and also when bound to its 42-bp target

operator in the *ttgDEF* and *ttgGHI* intergenic regions. The operator covers the -10 region of each promoter (Guazzaroni *et al.*, 2007b; Fillet *et al.*, 2009).

Each TtgV monomer has two domains, one comprising the HTH DNA binding domain at the carboxy terminal end, and an effector binding region at the central and N-termini of the protein (Lu *et al.*, 2010). The two domains are bridged by a linker, whose role is to serve as a signal transmission element between the two domains that are physically disconnected (Fillet *et al.*, 2011b). Residues R98 and E102 within the linker, that bridge both domains, are critical for the correct transmission of the signal from the effector binding pocket to the DNA binding domain. Once the transmission is achieved TtgV modifies its structure and is released from the DNA, at this point the RNA polymerase is able to bind the promoter regions and initiate *ttgG* and *ttgV* transcription (Guazzaroni *et al.*, 2005 and 2007a). Although a TtgV/effector co-crystal structure has not been obtained, comparison of the apo-TtgV structure with the structure of the TtgV-DNA complex showed a major re-arrangement in TtgV (Lu *et al.*, 2010), which is consistent with a model proposed above.

Regulation of the SrpABC efflux pump in *P. putida* S12 (homologous to the TtgGHI in DOT-T1E) is more complex. In this bacterium, two different regulators, SrpS (TtgV in DOT-T1E) and SrpR participate in the control of the expression of the efflux pump operon (Wery *et al.*, 2001; Sun *et al.*, 2011). In addition, two insertion elements *ISS12* and *ISPpu21* can insert into *srpS* blocking its expression and derepressing the efflux pump (Wery *et al.* 2001; Sun *et al.*, 2009). SrpS is a repressor of the efflux pump and SrpR is an

antirepressor which binds to SrpS in such a way that it inhibits the SrpS-DNA interaction or facilitates if prebound to the promoter region (Sun *et al.*, 2011).

Energy requirements

The presence of organic solvents in the media invokes cellular responses that in most cases are energy demanding. In *P. putida* DOT-T1E *P. putida* S12 and *E. coli* HG228, the presence of sub-lethal concentrations of solvents provokes the induction of genes involved in energy production as those that are part of the TCA cycle (Segura *et al.*, 2005; Domínguez-Cuevas *et al.*, 2006; Volkers *et al.*, 2006; Wijte *et al.*, 2011; Goodarzi *et al.*, 2010) reinforcing the hypothesis that solvent tolerance is an energy demanding process.

Conclusions

Bacteria use a wide variety of mechanisms to overcome organic solvent toxicity, some of these processes are restricted to the response of certain bacteria toward specific solvents, but some general processes can be inferred from data in the literature. In general, bacteria try to overcome the membrane fluidity imposed by organic solvents by allowing a denser packing of their membranes. However, envelope modifications are not sufficient to prevent entry of the solvents into the cell and this entry provokes the activation of an immediate general stress response, including the induction of several chaperones that refold proteins denatured by the solvent and activation of the oxidative stress response. While in general these mechanisms are enough to

adapt to low concentrations of organic solvent, when concentrations are higher, the removal of the solvents by efflux pumps that extrude these toxic compounds are required. Solvent tolerance is an expensive process from an energetic point of view and this is reflected by higher energy demands in the presence of these toxic compounds.

Recent research has mostly focused on the improvement of solvent-tolerance properties of the solventogenic bacteria *C. acetobutylicum* or the easily-manipulated *E. coli* and future approaches in the production of butanol or ethanol will include alternative platforms for biosynthesis of these compounds in solvent-tolerant bacteria (Nielsen *et al.*, 2009). Rühl and coworkers (2009) reported the growth of adapted *Pseudomonas putida* strains in the presence of up to 6% (vol/vol) butanol, the highest reported butanol concentration tolerated by a microbe. Improvement of solvent-tolerant strains for the production of fine chemicals should also blossom in the near future because bacteria can use inexpensive materials for the synthetic processes (Verhoef *et al.*, 2009). Some of the responses depicted above, such as cell surface changes, general stress responses or efflux of solvents has been proposed in Gram-positive bacteria, however, the mechanisms are yet to be elucidated and thus some unique, specific systems are to be expected (Torres *et al.*, 2011).

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Figures Legends

Figure 1. Model of an RND efflux pump based on the structure of its components. This model represents the possible assemblage of the ArcB (inner membrane pump) AcrA (periplasmic protein) and the TolC (outer membrane) protein. The illustration has been modified with permission from (Murakami *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 2. Response of *P. putida* DOT-T1E and isogenic mutants to a sudden solvent shock. Solvent tolerance in this strain is an adaptive process induced by low concentrations of toluene. Bacteria pre-exposed to toluene are highly resistant to a sudden solvent shock, in contrast with non-induced cells or cells with a deficiency in one of the solvent extrusion RND pumps. (For details see - -----).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the main mechanisms involved in the multifactorial solvent tolerance processes: Increased membrane packaging, set up of a stress response program, energy generation, and solvent extrusion.